

THE NEED FOR DIGITAL MARKETING IN THE SYSTEM IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11653930>

Abstract. The article reveals the role and importance of digital marketing research in the development of the activities of higher educational institutions of our country. The article also presents author's approaches to conducting digitized marketing research based on the study of the scientific work of foreign scientists on problems and their solutions.

Keywords: digital marketing, higher education institutions, digital marketing research, Internet, social networks.

One of the inevitable changes in marketing associated with the radical development of technology is digital marketing. Digital marketing plays an important role in the development of the company's brand today. In conditions of sharp competition, rapid changes in the behavior of future specialists require higher education institutions to revise strategies aimed at a consistent and systematic conduct of digitized marketing research.

Digital marketing research requires a number of field-specific knowledge and skills, which are areas related to Information Systems, marketing, and higher education [1]. Despite the fact that the number of studies carried out in this area increases from year to year, even today there are shortcomings in identifying the possibilities of digitization in business and understanding its participation in conceptualizing the business model.

Digital marketing plays an important role in promoting higher education institutions in the modern world. This allows higher education institutions to effectively communicate with prospective professionals, increase brand visibility, and attract prospective professionals.

Also, digital marketing research covers information systems, marketing and entrepreneurship [2]. Despite the research that is developing in this area, there are several problems that higher education institutions have with how to identify business opportunities and understand concepts in the business model. Because, in the literature on digitizing marketing research, there is no consistent terminology and specification of important components [3]. This can be explained by the fact that there is a consistent terminology in the scientific literature on this area, as well as shortcomings regarding important components.

The relevance of the study is that in recent years, higher education institutions remain an integral part of the main goal and life of modern youth. The competitive environment, on the other hand, creates an atmosphere of struggle between higher education institutions for future professionals, which in its place dictates that they practice the role and importance of digital marketing technologies for higher education institutions in an excellent study.

Previously, conducting marketing research took a lot of time and cost. Thanks to the Internet, marketing research has now evolved from paper surveys, one-on-one interviews and focus group discussions to a mobile, fast and more accessible research method. Digital marketing research uses devices such as computer technology to conduct interviews, telephone surveys, distribute surveys, and analyze product use. Also, marketing research uses social media by collecting and analyzing millions of posts on various social networking platforms to identify trends and provide more information about consumers [4].

Failure to use digital marketing or insufficient social media activity in higher education institutions can be a factor that prevents branding. While research in recommended groups for many years has been an effective source of information for marketing researchers to make marketing decisions, Internet networks are now a source of data for Digital marketing Research [5].

Today, all social groups are active on the internet, where they share their feedback with everyone [6]. Therefore, researchers seek relevant information on social networks, blogs, forums, reviews and other resources and determine the wishes and needs of customers [7]. This describes the analysis and evaluation of data from and through the World Wide Web, a digital marketing study [8]. This is done using digital data processing from manual data collection analysis to artificial intelligence.

Companies like Facebook and Google are constantly engaged in digital marketing on a truly scale [10]. They take advantage of all the possibilities to take into account the advantages and needs of their users, and then create an advertising profile that suits them very well. To do this, they always rely on the help of various improved algorithms, as well as artificial intelligence technologies, which are possible in the method of observation.

Artificial intelligence has now been able to penetrate deeper into it, along with searching for keywords in the text [11]. With this modern application, it will be possible to completely automatically check and analyze articles on the forum, posts and comments on social networks, blogs, and even images and videos for content.

Digital marketing research allows you to find offers that match your marketing strategy with [12]. With them, companies bring their products to the public in a properly oriented way to the target audience. Suitability testing of websites or applications is also done through marketing market research. Online surveys differ in content and structure from traditional surveys and are able to attract all internet users.

In conclusion, it can be noted that higher education is seen in the desire to reform the services market and create a highly qualified personnel training system that can find its place in the labor market in the training of a specialist, establish mutually beneficial cooperation of education with production enterprises and scientific organizations. research institutes. Digital marketing facilitates direct communication with educational institutions and consumers, expanding market share and raising awareness. It reinforces the role of digital marketing research to maximize the use of this data. So, the main goal of digital marketing research is to attract prospective professionals and improve their retention (taking into account needs, hoax-desires), track trends and trends, identify a new target audience, find approaches for new marketing campaigns.

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